

Thermal Calculation for Plasma as A Technique for Treatment of a Radioactive Aqueous Organic Sample as Well as Study on the Analysis of CaF_2 and BaF_2 Crystals' Elemental Composition and Optical Characteristics Before and After Neutron Irradiation

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Abstract

The idea of the developed closed nuclear fuel cycle allows for the development of solid products fit for long-term storage in addition to the disposal of all varieties of RW. The unique quality of RW is that their relative decontamination can only be accomplished by storing them for an extended period of time to allow the radionuclides within to decay [1].

The current technology for disposing of SNF processing waste (SNF PW) involves a lengthy, energy-intensive process that does not allow for the possibility of future use. It takes the form of water solutions with a low content of actinides, non-radioactive decay products (Mo, REE, etc.), and structural materials left over after the first extraction cycle [2].

Determining the impact of neutron radiation on the elemental composition of pure and Er^{3+} doped BaF_2 and CaF_2 crystals is one of the key goals of that research. High-quality declared crystal objects were obtained, and optical techniques were used to study them.

The JINR team performed methodological preparations on crystal model objects, neutron irradiation of samples, elemental composition studies using the PIXE method, and elemental depth profile studies using the RBS method both before and after fast neutron irradiation (2.5 MeV, dose $D = 10^{12}$ particles/cm²).

Introduction

The transmission coefficient of light through crystals was measured using the spectral ellipsometry complex "ELLIPS-1991" in the wavelength range 300-1100 nm at an incidence angle of 0° in the transmission mode. The measurement was carried out in two stages: the first – measurement of the standard (per lumen), the second – measurement of the crystal. The transmission $T_{\lambda} = I_{\text{sample}} / I_{\text{standard}}$ is computed from the ratio of the sample and standard signals [5].

A single-stage, high-speed approach for obtaining oxide compounds from SNF PW's dispersed water solutions is provided using gas-discharge plasma. However, the only method available for processing water solutions in plasma requires a significant amount of energy (up to 4 kW·h / kg) and is unable to provide the requisite composition for the chemical production of oxide compounds in air plasma without additional hydrogen reduction [2].

The effect on Tad for aqueous organic nitrate solutions based on organic compounds from reactor waste and ethanol (a) and acetone (b) of spent nuclear fuel content (RW SNF) is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Calculation of water-salt-organic matter combustibility indicators compositions made from waste from the spent nuclear fuel processing.

Optimization of system operation modes "HF generator-VHF plasma torch" are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Impact of the reactor impeller's input area and the VHF discharge power on the high-frequency generator-based plasma module's installation efficiency VChG8-60/13-01.

In this research work, the elemental composition of crystals of the composition $\text{CaF}_2 - X\% \text{ mol ErF}_3$ and $\text{BaF}_2 - Y\% \text{ mol ErF}_3$, where $X = 0.1, 0.5$ and 5.5 ; $Y = 0.1, 0.5$ and 5.0 were investigated. Using the accelerator EG-5 (JINR, Dubna, Russian Federation), the Rutherford Back Scattering (RBS) method was used to conduct the investigation. A 2 MeV energy level of 4He ions was employed. Throughout the experiment, the ion beam incident angle on the sample was $\alpha = 60^\circ$ and 90° , while the ion scattering angle was $\theta = 170^\circ$.

The SIMNRA modeling tool was used to process energy spectra and obtain a profile of element content by depth of near-surface layer in the samples that were studied [3,4].

For the near surface layer analysis of materials, Rutherford Backscattering Spectrometry (RBS) is a nuclear technique that is widely used. The energy of the backscattered projectiles following an ion bombardment of a target at an energy in the MeV range (often 0.5–4 MeV) is recorded by an energy-sensitive detector, typically a solid-state detector. RBS enables the quantification of a material's composition and the detailed depth profile of each element. RBS does not require reference samples and is a quantitative, nondestructive method. Parts-per-million (PPM) measurements demonstrate its exceptional sensitivity for heavy elements, and its decent depth resolution spans several nanometers.

Experimental and Practical Analysis

Analysis of crystals of CaF_2 composition with addition ErF_3

Figure 3 shows a photographic picture of samples of CaF_2 with ErF_3 addition in the transition state.

Fig.3. CaF_2 crystals with X mol% ErF_3 dopant.

b) 0.5 mol%; c) 5.5 mol%. The arrows show the kinematic boundaries of the elements.

The RBS spectra of ^4He ion backscattering from CaF_2 crystals with varying concentrations of alloying additives ErF_3 are displayed in Fig. 4: a) 0.1 mol%; b) 0.5 mol%; and c) 5.5 mol%. Er atoms are present in the near-surface layer of the crystal under study, as indicated by the step (Fig. 4) and the curve Er in the channels 600–800 region.

The intensity of the step increases with an increase in the dopant ErF_3 (Fig. 4, b, c), indicating a uniform distribution of Er atoms throughout the crystal's depth. Furthermore, two mild steps can be seen in the region of channels 400–600 on the spectra (Fig. 4), which correspond to the F and Ca atoms. Figure 5 and Table 1 display the atom concentration and distribution patterns along the crystal's depth CaF_2 : X mol% ErF_3 [5].

Table 1. Atomic concentration of elements in crystal CaF_2 with different concentration of ErF_3 before neutron irradiation.

Layer number	Depth, nm	Concentration of elements in the layer, atomic%		
CaF_2:0,1mol%ErF_3				
1	186	F	Ca	Er
2	838	63.94	36.01	0.05
3	1429	64.93	35	0.07
3	1429	64.91	34.99	0.1
CaF_2:0,5mol%ErF_3				
1	155	69	30	0.6
2	1242	67.3	32	0.7
3	1429	68.9	30	1.1
4	1429	69	30	1.3
CaF_2:5.5 mol%ErF_3				
1	15	63.5	35	1.5
2	1366	71	27	2
3	1429	67.5	30	2.5

As shown in Fig.3, in the analyzed objects (CaF_2 : X mol% ErF_3 , X = 0.1, 0.5, 5.5) the concentration of atoms Er, F and Ca in the layer up to 1,5 μm thickness practically does not change. It can be seen for impurity ErF_3 (Fig.3, d), the concentration increases nonlinear by 30% when moving deep over 1.5 μm .

Fig. 5. Distribution profiles of elements included in the crystal CaF_2 : X mol% ErF_3 obtained using the RBS method.

Neutron irradiation significantly changed the pattern of the distribution of elements over depth. There was a tendency to increase the F concentration and decrease the Ca concentration by more than 30% as the sample moved deep (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. RBS spectra of CaF_2 crystals with different concentrations ErF_3 : a) 0.1 mol%; b) 0.5 mol%; c) 5.5 mol% after irradiation with neutrons with energy of 2 MeV. The arrows show the kinematic boundaries of the elements.

The tendency rises in direct proportion to the concentration of impurities. As can be observed, the redistribution of elements becomes exponential for impurity concentration $X = 5.5\%$ mol, although being more (Fig. 7, a) or less (Fig. 7, b) linear in character for small concentrations (0.1-0.5).

Table 2. Atomic concentration of elements in the crystal CaF_2 with different concentration of ErF_3 after irradiation with neutrons with energy of 2 MeV.

Layer number	Depth, nm	Concentration of elements in the layer, atomic%		
$\text{CaF}_2:0,1\text{mol}\%\text{ErF}_3$				
		F	Ca	Er
1	155	59.94	40	6.00E-04
2	155	64.94	35	6.00E-04
3	155	65.94	34	6.00E-04
4	155	67.94	32	6.00E-04
5	155	70.94	29	6.00E-04
6	1087	72.94	27	6.00E-04
7	466	75.9	24	9.90E-04
8	1553	79.9	20	9.90E-04
$\text{CaF}_2:0,5\text{mol}\%\text{ErF}_3$				
1	155	69.4	30	0.6
2	1227	70.3	29	0.7
3	1429	68.8	30	1.2
4	1500	68.65	30.1	1.3
$\text{CaF}_2:5.5\text{ mol}\%\text{ErF}_3$				
1	15	40	55	5
2	62	65.7	32	2.3
3	86	68.7	29	2.3
4	86	69.7	28	2.3
5	155	65.3	32	2.7
6	1500	65.3	32	2.7

Fig. 7. The distribution profiles of the elements included in the crystal $\text{CaF}_2: X \text{ mol}\% \text{ErF}_3$ after irradiation with neutrons with an energy of 2 MeV, obtained using the RBS method.

On the RBS spectrum of the sample CaF_2 : 0.1 mol% ErF_3 (Fig. 6, a) irradiated with neutrons with energy 2 MeV (Dose $F = 10^{12}$ particles/cm²), a "saddle" is observed, which indicates deformation of the crystal surface after exposure to intense neutron flux [6].

At an impurity concentration of ErF_3 0.1% mol, the concentration of F atoms increases by 25%, and the concentration of Ca atoms decreases by 50% when moving deeper into the sample to 1.5 μm . This effect is not observed at concentrations of the impurity ErF_3 : $X = 0.5$ and 5.5 mol%. At an impurity concentration of 5.5 mol% ErF_3 , the diffusion mobility of Ca and F atoms increases after neutron irradiation. Interlayer interaction occurs at a depth of 65 nm (Fig. 7, c). In addition, there is a sharp decrease of 54% in the concentration of Er atoms in the crystal depth (Fig.7, d).

Optical transmission of crystals doped with a high concentration of ErF_3 ($X = 0.5 - 5.5\%$ mol, Fig. 8), much lower than in samples doped with a low concentration of ErF_3 ($X = 0.1$).

Fig. 8. Optical transmission spectra of transparent crystals CaF_2 : X mol% ErF_3 .

On the absorption spectra (Fig. 8), a pronounced monotone tendency to develop absorption bands in the optical and IR regions of the spectrum (peaks in the wavelength range of 470 nm, 530 nm, 650 nm and doublets in the region of 960-990 nm) is noticeable as the ErF_3 concentration increases.

Fig. 9. Spectra of optical transmission of crystals CaF_2 : X mol% ErF_3 before and after irradiation with neutrons with energy 2 MeV.

Analysis of crystals of BaF₂ composition with addition ErF₃

Figure 10 shows a photographic picture of samples of BaF₂ with ErF₃ addition in the transition state.

Fig. 10. BaF₂ samples with dopant ErF₃.

The concentration of dopants ErF₃ in crystals BaF₂ is shown by the RBS spectra in Fig. 11 as follows: a) 0.1 mol%; b) 0.5 mol%; c) 5.0 mol% (system BaF₂: X mol% ErF₃, X = 0.1, 0.5, 5.0). The spectra clearly show three peaks (kinematic boundaries) that correspond to the atoms Er, Ba, and F (Fig. 11). Table 3 and Fig. 12 present the distribution of elements F, Ba, and Er graphically [7].

Fig. 11. RBS spectra of BaF₂ crystals with different concentrations ErF₃: a) 0.1 mol%; b) 0.5 mol%; c) 5.0 mol%. Arrows show kinematic boundaries of elements.

It can be seen that the concentration of the elements present in the crystal is substantially dependent on the depth. The concentration of F atoms is monotonically reduced by about 7%, 21% and 8% for concentrations of 0.1 mol%, respectively; 0.5 mol% and 5.0 mol%, while the concentrations of the remaining elements either monotonically increase: Er (Fig. 10, a, b), Ba (Fig. 10, b, c) or remain unchanged (Ba, Fig. 12, a; Er, Fig. 12, c) [9].

Table 3. Atomic concentration of elements in crystal BaF₂ with different concentration of ErF₃ before neutron irradiation.

Layer Number	Depth, nm	Concentration of elements in the layer, atomic %		
BaF ₂ :0,1mol%ErF ₃		F	Ba	Er
1	98	73	25	2
2	311	65.5	31	3.5
3	274	64.8	31.5	3.7
4	366	66.2	30	3.8
5	500	68.2	28	3.8
6	500	68.1	28	3.9
BaF ₂ :0,5mol%ErF ₃				
1	36	98	1.3	0.7
2	54	94.1	5.3	0.6
3	146	81	9	10
4	183	75.5	12	12.5
5	500	75.5	13	11.5
6	500	77.5	11	11.5
BaF ₂ :5.0 mol%ErF ₃				
1	109	72.5	22.5	5
2	311	67	30	3

3	274	65.8	30.7	3.5
4	366	66.2	30	3.8
5	366	66	30	4
6	500	65.8	30	4.2

Moreover, in a sample with an impurity concentration of $X = 0.5\%$, the depth profiles for all elements change with the greatest dynamics (Fig.12, b): the concentrations of Ba and Er increase by 12-13%, while the concentration of F decreases by 21%. Such a distribution of elements in depth is probably due to the technological features of the process of obtaining them [8].

After being exposed to a 2 MeV dose of neutrons (i.e., 1012 particles/cm²), the distribution pattern of atoms along the depth drastically changed. The alignment of the element concentration in depth (Fig. 14) and the emergence of a saddle in the spectra of Fig. 14, a, b, which denotes surface deformation to a depth of roughly 100 nm, show a consistent pattern. It should be observed that heavier Er atoms diffuse to the sample's surface following irradiation, while lighter Ba atoms diffuse deeper, per the reported concentration profiles [10].

Fig. 12. Distribution profiles of the elements included in the crystal BaF₂ with different concentrations ErF₃: X mol% ErF₃, obtained using the RBS method.

On the RBS spectrum (Figure 13, a, b), a «saddle» is observed in the region of channels 700-800, which indicates deformation of the surface layer. No surface deformation was observed at a concentration of 5.0 mol% (Figure 11, c).

Fig. 13. RBS spectra of BaF₂ crystals with different concentrations ErF₃: a) 0.1 mol%; b) 0.5 mol%; c) 5.0 mol% after irradiation with neutrons with energy of 2 MeV. Arrows show the kinematic boundaries of elements.

The transmittance of crystals doped with an impurity of ErF₃ with a concentration of $X = 5.0$ mol% is more than 20 times lower than that of samples doped with ErF₃ with a concentration of 0.1- 0.5 mol% (Fig.15). As in the case of BaF₂ crystals, an increase in the concentration of ErF₃

leads to absorption peaks in the range of 520 cm^{-1} , 650 cm^{-1} , 800 cm^{-1} and 980 cm^{-1} , however, in the case of $\text{BaF}_2:\text{X mol\% ErF}_3$ this effect is very weakly expressed [10].

Fig. 14. Distribution profiles of elements included in the crystal $\text{BaF}_2:\text{X mol\% ErF}_3$ after irradiation with neutrons with energy 2 MeV, obtained using the RBS method.

Fig. 15. Crystal optical transmission spectra $\text{BaF}_2:\text{X mol\% ErF}_3$.

A comparison of the transmission spectra before and after irradiation with fast neutrons (Fig. 16) indicate a slight decrease in transmission and a shift of the frequency spectrum to the high-frequency region (by approximately 50 cm^{-1} for a concentration of $X = 0.5\text{ mol\%}$ (Fig. 16 b) and 500 cm^{-1} for a concentration of $X = 5.0\text{ mol\%}$ (Fig. 16 c) and the opposite effect for an ErF_3 concentration of about 0.1 mol\% (Fig. 16 a) [9].

Fig. 16. Crystal optical transmission spectra $\text{BaF}_2:\text{X mol\% ErF}_3$ before and after neutron irradiation with energy 2 MeV.

Conclusion

Reprocessing spent nuclear fuel after the extraction cycle yields reprocessing waste (RW SNF), an aqueous nitrate solution (raffinate) with the following composition: [1]: The remaining H_2O makes up 18,00%, along with HNO_3 , 0.07 percent Fe, 0.11 percent Nd, 0.10 percent Mo, 0.06 percent Y, 0.058% Zr, 0.04 percent Na, 0.039 percent Ce, 0.036% Cs, 0.031% Co, and 0.026% Sr.

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